

4Q51 frag. 100 + PAM 43.701 frag. 105 (2 Sam 12:14-16)

Eibert Tigchelaar, KU Leuven

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Characteristic of the Qumran Cave 4 manuscript 4Q51 (4QSam^a) is the large number of small fragments. Among the plates of unidentified fragments there are several that can be assigned to 4Q51. Thus also PAM 43.701 frag. 105 (DJD 33 Plate XL; IAA Plate 77, frag. 103) which can be placed to the right of 4Q51 frag. 100 lines 1-3 (DJD 17, p. 143, pl. XVIII). The join is textually assured, even though the fragments only join in line 1.

Transcribe now 4Q51 frags. 100-101 + PAM 43701 frag. 105 as follows, with the traces of PAM 43.701 frag. 105 in red

כי נאץ נאצ[ת] את דבר יהוה בדב[ר הזה ג]ם ה[בן הילוד] לך מות יומת וילך	1
נתן אל ביתו ויגוף אלוהים את [הילד א]שר ילד[ה אש]ת אוריה לדוד ויבקש	2
[דו]י[ד מן האלוהים בעד הנער וי]צם דוי[ד ויב]א וישכב בשק ארצה ויקומ[ו]	3

Join of top right section of 4Q51 frag. 100 with PAM 43701 frag. 105 screen captures of parts of
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-368216>
<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-492499>

Note that on image B-368216 4Q51 frags. 100 and 101 are positioned differently than in the final edition, reflected in the transcription above. Compare the image from DJD 17 plate XVIII:

Bibliography

DJD 17 Frank Moore Cross, Donald W. Parry, Richard J. Saley, and Eugene Ulrich, *Qumran Cave 4, XII: 1-2 Samuel*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 17. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2005

DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001.

IAA Israel Antiquities Authority

PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum